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INTEGRATIVE TAXONOMY OF *Merodon caerulescens* COMPLEX (Diptera: Syrphidae) – EVIDENCE OF CRYPTIC SPECIATION

ABSTRACT: In this research, we applied integrative taxonomy approach in order to delimit species of *Merodon caerulescens* species complex. Molecular analyses confirmed COI sequence divergence between the Rhodes and Crete populations. Additionally, ITS2 sequences show certain differences which should be additionally tested. 28S rRNA gene sequences once again proved to be too conserved for closely related species delimitation. Geometric morphometry results indicate differences in wings shape between males and females of the two islands populations. Additionally, subtle differences between the two populations in the body coverage and colouration of hairs are also observed. Thus, based on the all presented evidence we concluded that taxon *Merodon caerulescens* is a complex of two species, *M. caerulescens* (Rhodes) and *M. atricapillatus* sp. n. (Crete).

KEYWORDS: 28S rRNA, COI, ITS2, geometric morphometrics, island speciation, *Merodon caerulescens* complex

INTRODUCTION

Hoverflies comprise a high number of described species and they have a worldwide distribution. The species inhabit very diverse habitats from the sea level up to 3500 metres (Vujić et al., 2002; Barkalov and Ståhls, in preparation). Beside morphologically clearly defined species, Syrphidae family comprise morphologically very similar or almost identical species. So far, the largest number of cryptic species of syrphids has been recorded in the subfamily Eristalinae (Marcos-García et al., 2011; Popović et al., 2015; Ačanski et al., 2016;

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Šašić et al., 2016; Radenković et al., 2018), but also occur in the subfamily Syrphinae (Nedeljković et al., 2013, 2015; Vujić et al., 2013) and Microdontinae (Schönrogge et al., 2002).

An important improvement in the taxonomy of Syrphidae was achieved due to the application of molecular markers. The sequences of 3' and 5' regions of cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) gene are mostly used and many researchers combine them with sequential data of nuclear molecular markers such as nuclear genes for ribosomal RNA (rRNA) and the internal transcribed spacer 2 region (ITS2) (e.g. Pérez-Bañón et al., 2003; Massetti, 2006; Mengual et al., 2006, 2008a, b, 2015; Haarto and Ståhls, 2014). Further, the synergy of morphology, molecular data and geometric morphometry has made a significant contribution to the taxonomy of hoverflies (Nedeljković et al., 2013, 2015; Vujić et al., 2013; Ačanski et al., 2016; Šašić et al., 2016; Radenković et al., 2018).

Merodon aureus species group comprise 30 species distributed in Mediterranean region and mountain areas of southern Europe (Marcos-García et al., 2007; Vujić et al., 2007; Milankov et al., 2008; Radenković et al., 2011; Speight, 2014; Šašić et al., 2016; Veselić et al., 2017; Radenković et al., 2018). According to Šašić et al. (2016), the group comprise five subgroups (*M. aureus*, *M. dobrogensis*, *M. bessarabicus*, *M. chalybeus* and *M. cinereus* subgroup) and the two, independent species, *M. unguicornis* and *M. caerulescens*. The taxonomy of the *Merodon aureus* species group has long been considered a major challenge for taxonomists, taking into account the absence of consistent morphological differences between taxa. The structure of male genitalia is very simple and similar in all representatives of the group (Radenković et al., 2011, 2018; Šašić et al., 2016; Veselić et al., 2017), thus, it is not possible to determine species with certainty. However, recent studies indicate a high diversity of species of the *Merodon aureus* group due to the presence of cryptic species and/or species complexes (Šašić et al., 2016; Veselić et al., 2017; Radenković et al., 2018). In Šašić et al. (2016) and Radenković et al. (2018) the application of molecular methods together with geometric morphometry contributed to the description of two new species of *M. atratus* species complex and six new species of *M. luteomaculatus* species complex.

In this research, we focus on *Merodon caerulescens*, which is a species complex within *M. aureus* species group. The aim of this research is to explore the diversity of *Merodon caerulescens* species complex and to perform species delimitation in the spirit of integrative taxonomy by applying COI, ITS2, 28S rRNA gene sequences analyses and geometric morphometry of wings, in addition to morphological description.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Morphological studies

The present study is based on examination of all available material (459 specimens) of the *Merodon caerulescens* complex found in collections, both

published and unpublished, deposited in the museums and universities collections listed below. The following acronyms of museums and entomological collections are used in the text:

FSUNS – Faculty of Sciences, Department of Biology and Ecology, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

RMNH – Naturalis, National Museum of Natural History, Leiden, Netherlands

MZH – Finnish Museum of Natural History, Helsinki, Finland

NHMW – Museum of Natural History, Wien, Austria

ZHMB – Zoological Museum of Humboldt University, Berlin, Germany

ZMUC – Zoological Museum, Natural History Museum of Denmark, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

DNA extraction

For molecular analyses, the fresh adult specimens were collected using an entomological net while they were feeding on flowers or resting on leaves of terrestrial vegetation. The specimens data are presented in Table 1.

The genomic DNA was extracted using SDS extraction protocol described by Chen et al. (2010), with slight changes to the protocol.

We amplified 3' and 5'-regions of COI gene, D2-3 region of the 28S rRNA gene and ITS2 region. For 3'COI we used C1-J-2183 (also known as Jerry) and TL2-N-3014 (also known as Pat) primer pair (Simon et al., 1994), for 5'COI LCO1490 and HCO2198 primer pair (Folmer et al., 1994), for 28S rRNA gene region F2 and 3DR primer pair (Belshaw et al., 2001) and for ITS2 we used ITS2A and ITS2B primer pair (Beebe & Saul, 1995). The PCR reactions were performed as described in Radenković et al. (2018). PCR products were enzymatically purified using exonuclease I and shrimp alkaline phosphatase enzymes and sequenced in forward direction using the BigDye Terminator v.3.1 cycle sequencing kit (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, Ca, USA) on ABI 3730xl DNA Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, Ca, USA) at the Sequencing Service Laboratory of the Finnish Institute for Molecular Medicine (FIMM), Helsinki, Finland.

Sequence analyses

Sequences were aligned using the Clustal W algorithm as implemented in BioEdit 7.0.9.0 (Hall, 1999) with final adjustments by eye. The sequence diversity parameters, COI haplotypes and genotypes of the 28S sequences were calculated using DnaSP 5 software (Librado and Rozas, 2009), while the Median-joining (MJ) haplotype network (Bandelt et al., 1999) was constructed using PopART (<http://popart.otago.ac.nz>). We calculated average uncorrected sequence divergence value (p distance) and the best substitution model for sequence matrix (Tamura-3-parameter model, T92) using the MEGA 6 software

(Tamura et al., 2013). The software ABGD (Automatic Barcode Gap Discovery) (Puillandre et al., 2012) was used for COI sequences partitioning into hypothetical species based on distance calculation (uncorrected p distance, T92 distances and Kimura-2-parameter, K80 distances) and by applying default parameters (Pmin=0.001, Pmax=0.1, Steps =10, X (relative gap width) =1.5, Nb bins =20).

The parsimony analyses (MP) and phylogenetic tree construction were performed using NONA software (Goloboff, 1999) implemented in Winclada ASADO (Nixon, 2008) using the heuristic search algorithm (settings: mult*1000, hold/100, max trees 100000, TBR option enabled). Statistical support for the topology of the constructed phylogenetic trees was evaluated using the non-parametric bootstrap method with 1000 replicates calculated using Winclada. The Maximum Likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree was constructed using RAxML 8.2.8 (Stamatakis, 2014) by applying the general time-reversible (GTR) evolutionary model with a gamma distribution (Rodriguez et al., 1990), while statistical support for the clades was assessed using rapid bootstrap method with 1000 replicates. The trees were rooted on *Merodon albifasciatus* Macquart, 1842 (accession numbers for 3'COI and 5'COI: KU365486, KU365422).

Geometric morphometric analysis

Geometric morphometric analysis of wing shape was conducted on 36 specimens of the *M. caerulescens* complex (Table 1). The right wing of each specimen was used in the geometric morphometric analysis. Wings are archived and labelled with a unique code in the FSUNS collection, together with other data relevant to the specimens. Eleven homologous landmarks at vein intersections or terminations, –that could be reliably identified– were selected using TpsDig v2.05 (Rohlf, 2006).

Generalised least squares Procrustes superimposition was performed on the raw coordinates to minimise non-shape variations in location, scale and orientation of wings, and to superimpose the wings in a common coordinate system (Rohlf and Slice, 1990; Zelditch *et al.*, 2004) by employing MorphoJ v2.0 (Klingenberg, 2011). Principal component analysis (PCA) was carried out on the Procrustes shape variables to reduce the dimensionality of the dataset. Then, the stepwise discriminant analysis was employed to extract the subset of principal components (PCs) that are describing the highest overall classification percentage.

To explore wing shape variation among the taxa canonical variate (CVA) and discriminant function (DA) analyses were used. Superimposed outline drawings produced by MorphoJ software were used to visualize differences in mean wing shape among species pairs. All statistical analyses were performed in Statistica for Windows (Dell Statistica, 2015).

Table 1. The list of *Merodon* specimens used for molecular and geometric morphometrics analyses.

Taxon	Collecting locality	Sex	DNA ID	GenBank accession number COI	GenBank accession number 28S	GenBank accession number ITS2	Wing ID
<i>M. ambiguus</i> Bradescu, 1986	RS, Đerdap	♂	AU56	MH133974			
<i>M. aureus</i> Fabricius, 1805	IT, Ballino	♂	AU163	MH133978			
<i>M. chalybeus</i> Wiedemann, 1822	ES, Algeciras	♀	AU752	MH133976			
<i>M. cinereus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	AT, Alpes	♂	AU360	MH133993			
<i>M. dobrogensis</i> Bradescu, 1982	ROU, Mangalia	♂	AU415	MH133977			
<i>M. sapphous</i> Vujić, Pérez-Bañon et Radenković, 2007	TU, Isparta	♂	AU427	MH133975			
<i>M. unicolor</i> Strobl, 1909	ES, Sierra Nevada	♀	AU320	MH133979			
<i>M. atricapillatus</i> sp. n.	GR, Crete	♀	AU175	MH133987	MH137246		WM2232
		♀	AU176	MH133988	MH137247	MH137238	WM2233
		♀	AU178	MH133990	MH137249		WM2235
		♀					WM2237
		♀	AU181	MH133992	MH137251		WM2238
		♀					WM2228
		♀					WM2229
		♀					WM2230
		♀	AU177		MH137248		WM2234
		♂	AU179	MH133991	MH137250		WM2236
		♂					WM2231
		♂	AU106	MH133984	MH137243		
		♀					WM2218
♀					WM2224		
♂	AU102	MH133980	MH137239		WM2219		
♂					WM2217		
♀	AU107	MH133985	MH137244	MH137237	WM2226		
♀	AU108	MH133986	MH137245		WM2223		
♀					WM2220		
♀					WM2221		
♀					WM2222		
♀	AU103	MH133981	MH137240		WM2210		
♀	AU104	MH133982	MH137241		WM2211		
<i>M. caerulescens</i> Loew, 1869	GR, Rhodes	♀					WM2203
		♀				WM2205	
		♀				WM2206	
		♀				WM2207	
		♂	AU105	MH133983	MH137242		WM2202
		♂					WM2204
		♂					WM2208
		♂					WM2209
		♀					WM2225
		♀					WM2214
♀					WM2215		
♀					WM2216		
♂					WM2212		
♂					WM2213		

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Molecular evidence

The COI sequence analyses indicate that *Merodon caerulescens* is not a single species, but the complex of two cryptic and genetically divergent species. A set of 13 combined sequences of the 3' and 5' end of the COI gene was analyzed. The length of the aligned sequences is 1400bp. In phylogenetic tree construction, we additionally included representatives from different subgroups of *Merodon aureus* group, one sequence per species (see Table1). The species divergence is shown by MP and ML trees construction where the two populations (Rhodes and Crete) of *M. caerulescens* form two reciprocally monophyletic clades with medium to high bootstrap nodal support values (88/84 and 94/97) (Figure 1). Thus, we consider the Rhodes population as true *M. caerulescens* and population from Crete as a new species *M. atricapillatus* sp. n.

Figure 1. COI Maximum parsimony tree (333 steps, consistency index: 81, retention index: 84). The bootstrap values ≥ 50 are indicated near nodes, values from Maximum Likelihood tree are indicated in squares. Filled circles represent non-homoplasious characters, open circles are homoplasious characters.

Out of 1400 positions of the analyzed COI sequences, 16 are variable, while 11 positions are parsimony informative. The total number of haplotypes is 9 (Figure 2). The haplotype diversity (Hd) of the complex is 0.949, the average number of differences (K) is 5.769, and the nucleotide diversity (Pi) is 0.00412. The haplotypes of the two species form two haplotype groups on MJ network which are separated by seven mutational steps (Figure 2). The average uncorrected p distance value between the species (0.7%) is in the range of values recorded for cryptic, closely related hoverfly species (e. g. Marcos-García et al., 2011; Vujić et al., 2013; Popović et al., 2015; Nedeljković et al., 2015; Šašić et al., 2016; Radenković et al., 2018).

	COI haplotypes (DNA ID)	28S genotypes (DNA ID)
<i>M. caerulescens</i>	Hap1 (AU102, AU106), Hap2 (AU103, AU105), Hap 3 (AU104, AU108), Hap 4 (AU107)	I (AU102, AU103, AU105, AU106, AU108) II (AU104, AU107)
<i>M. atricapillatus sp. n.</i>	Hap5 (AU175), Hap6 (AU176), Hap7 (AU177), Hap8 (AU178, AU181), Hap9 (AU179)	II (AU175, AU176, AU177, AU178, AU179, AU181)

Figure 2. Median-joining network of COI haplotypes and 28S rRNA genotypes of *Merodon caerulescens* complex.

In order to define barcoding gap between the two species, we applied ABGD analysis of COI sequences which resulted in sequences partitioning into two groups which correspond to two *M. caerulescens* complex species (barcoding gap detected at 0.001 distance value). The same results were obtained by analyzing all three distance types (uncorrected p, T92, and K80).

The genetic divergence which is shown by COI sequence analyses is supported based on the ITS2 sequences. Assuming technical constraints in ITS2 amplification for *Merodon* specimens, ITS2 sequences were produced for only one specimen per species (AU107 and AU176). The sequences differ in gap region of 6 bp in *M. atricapillatus sp. n.* AU176 sequence comparing to *M. caerulescens* AU107 sequence (Figure 3). Namely, the AU107 sequence contains “AAAACG” motif in two copies, while AU176 contains only one copy. However, considering that only one specimen per species was tested we take this result with caution. We suspect that this difference might be important for species delimitation, although it is also possible that length variation in ITS2 sequences is an intraspecific phenomenon. For example, Mengual et al. (2006) found variability in a dinucleotide repeat region, AT₍₁₋₅₎ between Spanish *M. albifrons* specimens and interpreted it as intraspecific.

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      .....|.....|.....|.....|.....|.....|
                290      300      310      320
AU107 M. caerulescens   TATAGTAGCA TAAAAATAAA ACGAAAACGA AAACAAAAC
AU176 M. atricapillatus sp. n. TATAGTAGCA TAAAAAT--- ---AAAACGA AAACAAAAC

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Figure 3. The comparisons of ITS2 sequences of *Merodon caerulescens* and *M. atricapillatus*.

In contrast to the variability of COI and ITS2 sequences, the 28S rRNA gene sequences are typically more conservative and most often do not show a significant divergence between closely related species (Mengual et al., 2006; Patwardhan et al., 2014) which has also been shown in the *M. caerulescens* complex. A total of 13 sequences of the 28S rRNA gene of *M. caerulescens* complex were analyzed. The length of the aligned sequences is 585bp. Only 2 genotypes with a difference in one base position are defined (Gd = 0.5128). The genotype I is unique for *M. caerulescens*, while the genotype II is shared between the two species from *M. caerulescens* complex (Figure 2).

Geometric morphometric evidence

Molecular results were supported by high significant wing shape differentiation within *Merodon caerulescens* species complex. Principal component analysis (PCA) carried out on the Procrustes shape variables produced 18 PCs from which 16 describe the highest overall classification percentage of investigated taxa, and are used in further analyses. DA showed that *M. caerulescens* and *M. atricapillatus* sp. n. differ highly significantly in wing shape (males: $F_{16,29} = 4.099$; $p < 0.01$; females $F_{16,29} = 5.7527$; $p < 0.01$). All specimens were correctly classified to *a priori* defined groups, which additionally strengthens the interspecific discrimination. Canonical variates analysis produced three highly significant axes (CV1: Wilks' Lambda = 0.00805; $\chi^2 = 173.5858$; $p < 0.01$; CV2: Wilks' Lambda = 0.0987; $\chi^2 = 83.3734$; $p < 0.01$; CV3: Wilks' Lambda = 0.3987; $\chi^2 = 33.1061$; $p < 0.01$). The first canonical axis depicts the sexual dimorphism, while CV2 clearly separated *M. caerulescens* from *M. atricapillatus* sp. n. (Figure 4A). The attractiveness of the insect's wings in integrative taxonomic studies is primarily connected to the fact that wing shape is controlled by genes (Moraes et al., 2004; Mezey & Houle, 2005; Dworkin & Gibson, 2006; Yeaman et al., 2010), which makes them important character for separating species. Over the past few years the geometric morphometric analysis of wing shape has proved to be significant in the field of new hoverfly species discovery (Nedeljković et al., 2013, 2015; Vujić et al., 2013; Ačanski et al., 2016; Šašić et al., 2016; Radenković et al., 2018). Moreover, in all of the above-mentioned studies, geometric morphometrics results were well supported by molecular results.

The superimposed outline drawings depict the differences in mean wing shape among each species which are the most obvious among males, with longer wings of *M. caerulescens* (Figure 4B). We can assume that clearer disparities of male wing shapes compared to female can be related to flight ability and, moreover, male species specific courtship song (Cowling and Burnet, 1981; Stubbs and Falk, 1983; Sacchi and Hardersen, 2013; Menezes et al., 2013; Outomuro et al., 2013). Generally speaking, the flies use their wings for producing courtship songs which have an important role in sexual selection and species recognition (Saarikettu et al., 2005; Routtu et al., 2007).

Figure 4. Shape variability among species of the *M. caerulescens* complex. A) Scatter plot of individual scores of CV1 and CV2. B) Superimposed outline drawings showing differences in average wing shape for each species pair. Differences between the species were exaggerated five-fold to make them more visible.

Morphological description

The species of the *Merodon aureus* group are small-sized (8–13 mm) with a short, rounded abdomen, a distinct spike on the hind trochanter in males, and a characteristic structure of the male genitalia: posterior surstyle lobe with parallel margins and rounded apex and a narrow, elongated, sickle-shaped hypandrium without lateral sclerite of aedeagus (see in Šašić et al., 2016: Figure 1). The *Merodon caerulescens* (sensu Šašić et al., 2016) is taxon with strong blue body lustre, mesonotum at least near wing base with the black pile, tibiae and tarsi predominantly black, tergites uniformly dark, tergites III and IV predominantly covered with the black pile.

Merodon caerulescens Loew, 1869

Type material. LECTOTYPE. Greece: 1♂, Rhodes, leg. Erber, (ZHMB). PARALECTOTYPES. Greece: 2♂♂, Rhodes, leg. Erber, (ZHMB).

Additional material. Greece, Rhodes: 2♂♂, 2♀♀, (NHMW). 1♂, 1♀, leg. Bgst. (NHMW). 1♂, leg. Erber, (det. P.H.v Doesburg, 1964: *Lampetia caerulescens*) (RMNH). Kattavia: 05.iv.1971, 3♀♀, (RMNH), 6♂♂, 1♀, leg. V.S.vd Goot (RMNH), 1♀, leg. V.S.vd Goot, J.W.A. Lucas (RMNH); 09.iv.1971, 5♀♀, (RMNH), 1♂, leg. V.S.vd Goot (RMNH). 1♀, Laerma, 08.v.1987, leg. V.S.vd Goot (RMNH). 1♂, Lahania, 08.iv.1971, leg. V.S.vd Goot (RMNH). Lindos, 04.iv.1971: 16♀♀, (RMNH), 1♀, leg. C. Claussen, (RMNH), 2♂♂, 1♀, leg. J.A.W. Lucas, V.S.vd Goot (♀ZMC, ♂RMNH), 25♂♂, 43♀♀, leg. V.S.vd Goot, (RMNH), 1♂, leg. V.S.vd Goot (NHMW); 06.iv.1971: 1♂, 1♀, (RMNH), 14♂♂, 64♀♀, leg. V.S.vd Goot (RMNH), 1♀, leg. V.S.vd Goot (NHMW); 08.iv.1971:

15♂♂, 20♀♀, leg. V.S.vd Goot (RMNH), 1♂, leg. J.A.W. Lucas, V.S.vd Goot (ZMC); 5♂♂, 7♀♀, 09.iv.1971, leg. V.S.vd Goot (RMNH); 2♂♂, 11.iv.1971, leg. V.S.vd Goot (RMNH); 2♀♀, 13.iv.1968, (ZMC); 1♀, 15.iv.1970, leg. V.S.vd Goot (RMNH); 2♀♀, 27.iii.1970, leg. V.S.vd Goot (RMNH); 1♀, 30.iii.1970, leg. V.S.vd Goot (RMNH). Loutanis river, Afantou – Archangelos: 1♀, 01.iv.2012, leg. A. Vujić, L. Likov (FSUNS); 2♂♂, 1♀, 15.iv.2012, leg. A. Vujić, L. Likov (FSUNS). 4♂♂, 6♀♀, Near Butterfly Valley, 17.iv.2012, leg. A. Vujić, L. Likov (FSUNS). 5♀♀, nr. Archipoli, 10.iv.2012, leg. A. Vujić, L. Likov (FSUNS). 1♀, nr. Kolympia, 08.iv.2012, leg. A. Vujić, L. Likov (FSUNS). 1♂, 2♀♀, Petaloudes, 12.iv.1971, leg. V.S.vd Goot (RMNH). Profitis, Ilias: 1♂, 23.iv.1970, leg. v. Ooststroom, (RMNH); 2♂♂, 3♀♀, 16.iv.2012, leg. A. Vujić, L. Likov (FSUNS). 1♂, Agios Nicholas Fountoukli, 11.iv.2004, leg. C. Lange, J. Ziegler (ZHMB). 1♂, Emponas, 15.iv.2004, leg. C. Lange, J. Ziegler (ZHMB). 1♂, Mesanagros, 08.iv.2004, leg. C. Lange, J. Ziegler (ZHMB).

Range and preferred habitat. Rhodes island (Greece); open, grassy areas in pine forest or Mediterranean scrub.

Merodon atricapillatus Šašić, Ačanski et Vujić sp. n.

Figure 5. *Merodon atricapillatus* sp. n. Habitus, dorsal view: A) male, B) female. Head, lateral view: C) male, D) female. E) Abdomen, male, lateral view. F) Hind leg, lateral view. Scale=1 mm.

Type material. HOLOTYPE: Greece: 1♂, Crete, Lasithi, Sissi, 23.iv.2014, leg. A. Vujčić (FSUNS). PARATYPE: (FSUNS). Greece, Crete: Heraklion, 2 km S Chersonisos: 1♂, 19.iv.1984 (FSUNS), 1♀, 16.x.1987, 3♂♂, 05.iv.1985. 2♂♂, 8♀♀, Lasithi, Sissi, 23.iv.2014, leg. A. Vujčić (FSUNS). Sisi near Malia: 2♀♀, 03.iv.1983, leg. C. Claussen (RMNH), 2♂♂, 08.iv.1983, leg. C. Claussen (RMNH); 1♀, Stalis, 21.iv.1988, leg. J. Mahler, E. Torp (ZMC).

Additional material. Greece, Crete: Heraclion: 2 km S Chersonisos: 29♂♂, 7♀♀, 03.iv.1986, 4♂♂, 14♀♀, 16-19.iv.1984, 10♂♂, 5♀♀, 18.iv.1987, 9♂♂, 2♀♀, 27.iii.1986: 2♀♀, 2 km W Limenas Chersonisos, 27.iv.1984; Chersonisos: 20♂♂, 05.iv.1985, (1♂ leg. C. Claussen, MZH), 1♂, 9♀♀, 11.iv.1985, (2♀♀ leg. C. Claussen, MZH); Limenas Chersonisos: 2♀, 30.iii.1986, 2♀♀, 20.iv.1987; 2♂♂, Potamies, 24-26.iv.1984; 3♂♂, 1♀, 3 km NW Potamies, 07.iv.1985. Lasithi: 18♂♂, 7♀♀, Sissi, 3-8.iv.1983; Sisi near Malia, 1♀, 03.iv.1983, leg. J.A.W. Lucas (RMNH), 1♀, 08.iv.1983, leg. J.A.W. Lucas (RMNH), 2♂♂, 08.iv.1983, leg. J.A.W. Lucas (RMNH).

Diagnosis. Species with bluish body reflection; mesoscutum with black pile on posterior half, at least near wing basis; hind femur with whitish pile, except apical fourth with black ones (in *M. caerulescens* more black pilosity), tergite II covered with pale pile in male (in *M. caerulescens* posterior margin with black pilosity). Similar to *M. caerulescens*, from which it differs by molecular data, wing morphometry and distribution.

Body size. Length: body = 9 mm; wing = 8 mm (n = 15).

Description. MALE (Figure 5ACEF). Head (Figure 5C). Antenna orange-brown; basoflagellomere reddish, 1.3–1.5 times longer than pedicel, dorsal margin concave between the arista and the apex, apex acute; arista yellow basally, as long as pedicel and basoflagellomere together. Face and frons shiny black with bluish lustre, covered with long whitish pile. Oral margin bare, with blue lustre. Vertical triangle isosceles, shiny black, covered with long black pile. Eye contiguity about 12 ommatidia long. Ocellar triangle isosceles. Eye pile long, dark in the upper third. Occiput shiny, bluish, except for along eye margin with a narrow stripe of white microtrichia; covered with whitish pile. Thorax. Mesonotum bluish with strong metallic reflections, predominantly covered with long, dense, erect pale pile, except black pile present on the posterior half of mesoscutum, at least near wing basis; mesoscutum with three very weak longitudinal stripes of dark brown microtrichia in anterior half. Posterior anepisternum, anepimeron and dorsal part of katapisternum with long whitish-yellow pile. Wing light brownish, with yellow veins. Dorsal and ventral calypters brownish. Haltere with light brown pedicel and dark brown capitulum. Femora black with pale apex; pilosity of fore femur predominately pale, mid femora with mixed black and pale pile; hind femur predominantly covered with yellow pile except few black ones in the apical 1/4 (Figure 5F). Tibiae predominantly dark except yellowish basal third and top; tarsi dark brown dorsally and yellow brown ventrally; covered in yellow pile with some intermixed black ones (hind tarsi dorsally can have more black pile). Hind trochanter with inner spike ending in two angular points (one corner more protruded). Abdomen (Figure 5E). Oval, slightly longer than mesonotum; black

with blue metallic reflections. Tergites without microtrichose bands. Tergite II completely covered with yellow pile; tergites III and IV predominately covered with black pile except lateral sides. Sternites shiny black, covered with long light yellow pile, except for a few black pile on sternite IV. Genitalia. Similar to all other species of the *aureus* group.

FEMALE (Figure 5BD). Similar to the male except for normal sexual dimorphism and in the following characteristics: ocellar triangle equilateral. Vertex with black pile. Mesoscutum with less black pilosity, in some specimens completely pale. Hind trochanter without a spike. Pilosity on abdomen shorter than in male; tergites II – IV with more black pile in female than in male.

Etymology. The word *atricapillatus* refers to the important diagnostic character of the species. The Latin adjective ater means black, and refers to the colour of long pile (Latin noun capillatus means long hairs) on mesonotum of this species.

Range and preferred habitat. Crete island (Greece); Mediterranean scrub along coastal zone.

CONCLUSION

Based on the presented evidence it is possible to distinguish two species within *Merodon caerulescens* species complex: *M. caerulescens* and *M. atricapillatus* sp. n. The two species are endemic to the Aegean islands Rhodes and Crete. The speciation in *M. caerulescens* complex is probably a consequence of allopatric processes which conditioned the reduction of gene flow between the two island populations. Molecular evidence based on COI sequences and geometric morphometric evidence both support the two-species concept. COI divergence (0.7%) indicate recent speciation. 28S rRNA gene sequences are not of much importance, considering a low level of variability, while the ITS2 sequences variability remains to be additionally tested.

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ИНТЕГРАТИВНА ТАКСОНОМИЈА *Merodon caerulescens*
КОМПЛЕКСА (Diptera: Syrphidae) – ДОКАЗИ О КРИПТИЧНОЈ
СПЕЦИЈАЦИЈИ

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РЕЗИМЕ: У овом истраживању примењен је приступ интегративне таксономије у циљу раздвајања врста *Merodon caerulescens* комплекса. Молекуларне анализе потврђују дивергенцију COI секвенци између популација са грчких острва Родос и Крит. Показане су и разлике у ITS2 секвенцама које је потребно додатно тестирати. Секвенце 28S рРНК гена су се још једном показале као сувише конзервативне за раздвајање блиско сродних врста. Резултати геометријске морфометрије указали су на разлике у облику крила између мужјака и женки две анализиране острвске популације. Додатно, суптилне разлике између поменутих популација видљиве су у покривености тела длакама и њиховој обојености. На основу свих изнетих резултата могуће је закључити да је *Merodon caerulescens* комплекс две врсте: *M. caerulescens* (Родос) и *M. atricapillatus* sp. n. (Крит).

КЉУЧНЕ РЕЧИ: 28S, COI, ITS2, геометријска морфометрија, острвска специјација, *Merodon caerulescens* комплекс